

INTERNAL STRESSES AND DIMENSIONAL CHANGES DURING THERMAL CYCLING OF WHISKER-REINFORCED Mg-Li

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ABSTRACT

Dilatometry has been used on an extruded Mg-11wt%Li/20vol%SiC whisker composite. The matrix is single phase bcc with a low yield stress and fast diffusion kinetics. Cycling between room temperature and 310°C leads to a net elongation parallel to the direction of whisker alignment, giving a strain of about $3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ per cycle. This has been explained on the basis of internal stress distribution, leading to a greater degree of plastic flow during the cooling part of the cycle (when it causes expansive deviation from elastic behaviour) and to more significant vacancy transport, so as to relax the (compressive) hydrostatic matrix stress, over the higher temperature part of the cycle. The relative importance of these two effects is not clear at this stage.

INTRODUCTION

There is considerable current interest in the behaviour of fibrous metal-based composites under conditions of thermal cycling, with and without simultaneous external loading. Part of this interest stems from the potential for producing metallic material with very low coefficients of thermal expansion, for example by incorporating fibres with low or negative expansivities such as carbon [1]-[3]. However, it is now well-established that thermal cycling can lead to pronounced dimensional changes and microstructural degradation in MMCs. A distinction should be drawn between cases in which this can be at least partially ascribed to microstructural changes, such as reaction product formation or Ostwald ripening effects [4]-[8], and those where the effects are unambiguously due to internal stresses caused by thermal expansion mismatch [9]-[12]. These stresses can stimulate various stress relaxation phenomena, leading to deviations from elastic behaviour, even for small temperature changes. It is also common to observe irreversible dimensional changes, even without any applied stress. Thermal cycling has been reported by several workers [9], [13]-[16] to cause progressive length changes in aligned fibrous composites, an effect sometimes referred to as strain-ratcheting [16].

In detail, some of the experimental data are potentially confusing. Dumant et al [14] indicate that the net strain per cycle in aluminium reinforced with 50% continuous carbon fibre can be of either sign. Patterson and Taya [9] on the other hand, report a 6% length increase (and corresponding thickness decrease) after 1000 cycles of Al(2124) with 15 vol% of SiC whiskers aligned parallel to the specimen length. This only occurred, however, with an upper temperature of 400°C: when this was increased to 500°C, no dimensional changes resulted. Other workers [7] have reported pronounced hysteresis, ascribed to the temperature dependence of the yield stress, but no net length change in a cycle. There is a shortage of data about the effect of fibre volume fraction; Petrasek and Signorelli [13] have reported that the net strain per cycle increases as this is raised, while Noda et al [15] report the reverse. There seems to be no systematic information about the effect of aspect ratio in a given system.

Relevant theoretical models may be divided into those analysing elastic stress states (and hence composite expansion coefficients) resulting from thermal misfit strains, and those predicting how the system will relax and undergo plastic deformation in response to these stresses. In the former category, a range of models have been proposed for different inclusion geometries [17], [18]. Short fibre systems have been extensively modelled by means of the Eshelby equivalent homogeneous inclusion method. For example, Takao and Taya [19] have shown that use of a mean aspect ratio will lead to a good approximation for the composite expansion coefficient, (irrespective of the nature of the aspect ratio distribution), whereas Takao [20] has demonstrated that the value is sensitive to the degree of fibre misorientation.

Among the various models describing departure from elastic behaviour is that of Garmong [21], which treats a continuous system on the basis of matrix creep and predicts a strain per cycle which increases with the volume fraction and aspect ratio of fibre. Wakashima and co workers [5], [15] on the other hand, assume an elastic/perfectly plastic matrix, with interfacial sliding, and predict that the net strain per cycle decreases as the fibre volume fraction is raised - in agreement with data for the copper-tungsten system [13]. These are

essentially one-dimensional models, but Min [16], [22] has produced an analytical plane stress model in which a matrix plasticity constitutive equation can be incorporated, while Taya and Mori [23] have developed an Eshelby-type model in which the average matrix stress is monitored at intervals during the thermal cycle and the possibility of both creep and plastic deformation of the matrix is considered. They predict an increase in net strain per cycle with both fibre volume fraction and fibre aspect ratio. The importance of understanding the stress relaxation mechanisms has also been emphasized by Withers et al [24], who noted that the kinetics of isothermal decay of internal matrix strain in whisker-reinforced aluminium did not fit a single rate constant and may involve both plastic flow and mass transport by vacancy motion. This type of comprehensive approach may well be necessary, as competitive stress relaxation mechanisms may be operative in different parts of the thermal cycle, depending on the stress state and temperature.

Finally, a number of models have been proposed [16], [25]-[27] to describe the effect during loading of superimposed thermal cycling, which can dramatically enhance the creep rates [28]-[30]. However, these models may not be usefully applicable to unstressed cycling. For example, although the model of Derby [27] gives fair agreement with some experimental observations [28], it predicts no net dimensional strain in the absence of applied stress, which is contrary to most experimental data. It has been pointed out [29] that, depending on rates of temperature change, internal stresses from thermal misfits are likely to be more transient than those from applied stresses and a universal model applicable to both dominant and negligible applied stress cases will need to describe the kinetics of stress relaxation (as a function of temperature) with some accuracy.

In the present paper, dimensional changes are measured for a Mg-11wt%Li/20vol%SiC_w composite. This matrix is single phase bcc and exhibits creep under modest loads, even at room temperature [32]. Creep studies [33] have suggested that dislocation climb, controlled by core or interfacial diffusion (at least up to about 200°C) is the rate-determining deformation mechanism. Under the conditions of the creep tests, the contribution to the internal stress state from differential thermal expansion did not seem to be affecting the creep behaviour, suggesting that those stresses were being relaxed relatively quickly. The aim of the present investigation was to identify the effect of these stresses on dimensional changes in the presence of such rapid relaxation.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material composed of 20vol%SiC whiskers in a matrix of Mg-11wt%Li was produced by preparation of a whisker preform (with silica binder), squeeze infiltration and extrusion, all under controlled atmosphere. The details of these procedures, and microstructural characteristics, are given elsewhere [33], [34]. The number- and volume-averaged whisker lengths were found to be 5.75 μm and 8.25 μm respectively, while the corresponding aspect ratio values were 12.4 and 11.8 [33]. Although generally exhibiting good alignment and homogeneity, the material contained some large equiaxed particles and there were regions in which noticeable fibre misorientation could be observed, particularly where the local volume fraction of whiskers was somewhat enhanced.

The individual expansivities of both matrix and whiskers were measured by neutron diffraction, at ILL Grenoble, using Mg-Li {110} and SiC{111} reflections on the D1A diffractometer work station. The alloy specimen was in the form of a cylinder of length 12 mm and diameter 8 mm, while the whiskers were simply an as-received agglomerate. After a period of 60 minutes for thermal equilibration, counting was carried out for a total period of about 15 minutes at each temperature. A composite specimen was also examined. Unfortunately, monitoring of the changing internal stresses was hampered by the high thermal inertia of the furnace employed which led to the masking of stress relaxation effects by prolonged thermal transients.

A dilatometer (Jenkins Instruments model J1000) with an operating range up to 1000°C and a flowing argon atmosphere, was employed for the length change measurements (made to a precision of about $\pm 1\mu\text{m}$.) For the unreinforced matrix, cylinders of length about 40mm and diameter 10mm were used, while the composite specimens were about 32mm long. The transverse expansion behaviour was examined by stacking two short cylinders with flat surfaces normal to the end faces, machined so as to be accurately parallel to one another. The net length in the measurement direction was about 13mm. (As the extrusion billet was only 10mm in diameter, this arrangement was chosen as a compromise between maximum specimen length and minimum

number of mating surfaces.) Thermal cycling was carried out at heating and cooling rates between about 0.01 K s^{-1} and 1 K s^{-1} , with dwell periods of up to 6 hours. Specimen temperatures were recorded via a thermocouple embedded in the specimen to a depth of about 5 mm. Length changes were sensed via a quartz tube coaxial with this thermocouple. Runs with unreinforced specimens were used, not only to measure $\alpha(T)$ for the matrix, but also to monitor any possible contribution to the recorded length change from specimen oxidation.

RESULTS

The neutron diffraction data indicated a constant rate of change of interplanar spacing with temperature for both whiskers and matrix. Data are shown in Fig. 1. These indicate α values of $4.3 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $35 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ respectively. This latter value may be compared with the dilatometric data shown in Fig. 2, in which it can be seen that the matrix expansion coefficient remains approximately constant over this temperature range. The value can be estimated from this graph as about $38.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$. It may also be noted that there is no detectable irreversibility in the curves, indicating that oxidation was negligible in this case. As the heating and cooling rates were relatively slow (0.1 K s^{-1}), and the figures for both peak temperature (310°C) and upper dwell period (3 hours) were relatively high, it may be concluded that oxidation should not have been significantly influencing any of the curves produced, at least for the axial specimens.

Figure 1. Neutron diffraction data for (a) matrix and (b) silicon carbide whiskers

Figure 2. Dilatometer trace for unreinforced matrix

Figure 3. Dilatometer trace for axial composite

In Fig. 3, dilatometric data are shown for a single cycle with the axial composite. This shows pronounced hysteresis: an initial high expansivity fell above about 120°C and remained fairly constant up to the arrest temperature of about 310°C. Holding at this temperature produced a negligible length increase. On cooling, a similar pattern was repeated in reverse, with the α value falling off from an initially high value after a temperature decrement of about 80°C or so. The final length was close to the initial value.

Various multiple cycle experiments were carried out, with different heating/cooling rates (up to a maximum of about 1 K s⁻¹) and dwell periods. In general, it was found that the curves were rather insensitive to these variables, suggesting that the relaxation of internal stresses was going to some exhaustion point at a rate sufficient to match the rate of stress generation. However, cycles after the first differed from it in that, while the shapes were broadly similar, the length did not return to its original value and a positive net strain per cycle (of about 3 10⁻⁴) was established. Typical curves are shown in Fig. 4, together with the recorded variations of both strain and temperature with time. It can be seen that, although the major part of the net strain arises during the thermal cycle, a proportion (~ 20%) occurs during the subsequent dwell at room temperature. Data for the transverse specimens exhibited some hysteresis. Fig.5 shows limited evidence of expansive deviation from elastic behaviour during heating and contractive deviation during cooling. Slight indications were detectable of expansion during holding at high temperature and contraction at low temperature.

Figure 4. (a) Dilatometer trace and (b) corresponding strain and temperature histories for three cycles with the axial composite specimen

Figure 5. Dilatometer trace for the transverse composite

Figure 6. Calculated expansivities

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

A first step to understanding the observed behaviour is to establish the expected axial and transverse expansivities for the composite in the elastic state. An Eshelby model (based on ellipsoidal inclusions) has been employed, following established procedures, such as those outlined by Takao and Taya [9]. The composite expansivities can be computed for any (volume-averaged) fibre aspect ratio, given the elastic constants and expansivities for the two constituents. The results are shown in Fig. 6, which was obtained using handbook Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio values for the whiskers of 490 GPa and 0.17. Corresponding figures for the matrix are not readily available, but it may be inferred from published data [32] for this matrix with precipitates present that E is probably close to 40 GPa, while ν is unlikely to differ markedly from a figure of 0.3. Figures of $36.75 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (mean of dilatometer and neutron diffraction values) and $4.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ (neutron diffraction only) were used for the expansivities of the two phases. The fibre aspect ratios employed to produce the curves shown correspond to the measured value (12) and a lower figure of 4 (designed broadly to represent the effect of extraneous large particles and misoriented whiskers). It can be seen that, for the volume fraction concerned (20%), the appropriate axial and transverse expansivity values are about 15 and $33 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the higher aspect ratio and 20 and $31 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for the lower value.

Fig.7 Schematic illustration of the changes in internal stress state during cycling

Taking $20 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ as an approximate figure expected for elastic axial expansion, comparison can now be made with the experimental curves. Qualitative interpretation can be attempted with the help of the schematic diagram in Fig. 7. It appears that heating at the start of the cycle gives rise to elastic expansion. This can be explained as a regime in which the internal stresses from contraction are reversed, with no local yielding taking place. At some point, the matrix will yield, primarily under axial compression (although the radial compression and hoop tension would also need to be taken into account in a quantitative model). Extension then continues with simultaneous yielding, giving a lower axial expansivity. It is expected that the deviatoric component of the local matrix stress state will decrease everywhere as the temperature rises and probably reaches a very small value in this matrix at around 300°C . The hydrostatic components of the stress states (now largely compressive in the matrix and uniformly tensile in the whiskers) cannot be relaxed by plastic flow, although Withers et al [24] have outlined reasons why their relaxation by vacancy transport should be

easier with whiskers than for particulate composites. The observed isothermal axial expansion may thus be at least partly associated with some dilatational relaxation. This would be consistent with the (small) observed transverse expansion during this period, since this type of relaxation will result in a net volume increase (as the strains in the whisker are smaller than those in the matrix).

During cooling, the reverse processes take place, although the initial elastic period is shorter because the starting stresses are small and a smaller deviatoric stress is now sufficient to promote yielding. Rather greater plastic flow (now tending to elongate the composite axially) will therefore tend to occur, when compared with the corresponding tendency to cause contraction during heating. Furthermore, dilatational relaxation, which could now cause an axial (and - lesser - lateral) contraction will probably be entirely absent, as the temperature will be too low during the part of the cycle when the matrix hydrostatic stress is strongly tensile. Indeed, axial expansion can apparently occur during holding at room temperature, presumably because (climb-assisted) dislocation motion under the influence of shear stresses had not gone to completion during the latter part of the cooling cycle. The transverse data do not appear to be entirely consistent with the above, in that a net contraction per cycle has not yet been detected. However, the limited specimen length, and presence of multiple surfaces, might have had the effect of rendering oxidation more significant, masking the effect. In any event, the magnitude of the changes is expected to be smaller than in the axial direction. It is clear that more comprehensive data are needed.

It should be noted that the net strain per cycle appears to be about 3×10^{-4} , which may be compared with the value recorded [9] for an Al(2124) matrix of about 0.6×10^{-4} . As the current matrix is expected to exhibit both a low yield stress and fast diffusion kinetics [35], this does not allow firm conclusions to be drawn about the relative importance of plastic flow and vacancy transport mechanisms. Although creep studies [33] have indicated dislocation mechanisms to be dominant, the situation is then different in that a deviatoric stress state is maintained. Vacancy transport may become significant in the present case after a hydrostatic stress state has been approached. Further work is needed to clarify this point.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work forms part of a project supported by BP plc. The authors are grateful to Dr.A.Begg, Dr.C.W.Brown and Mr.J.G.Robertson, of BP Research Centre, Sunbury on Thames, for helpful discussions. The neutron diffraction work at ILL was supported by the SERC via Rutherford Appleton Laboratories. The collaboration of M.Soubeyroux of ILL is gratefully acknowledged. Mr.P.J.Withers of the Materials Science Department, Cambridge, was also involved in these measurements and has in addition taken part in a number of useful discussions.

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